

Synthesis and structural characterization of a cyanide-bound heterodinuclear FeCo complex

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Abstract : A novel cyanide-bound heterodinuclear Fe^{III}/Co^{III} complex, [Co(phen)₂(CN)₂][Fe(pzqc)(CN)₃] \cdot 2 \cdot 5H₂O (**1**), where Hpzcq is 8-(pyrazine-2-carboxamido)quinoline, has been synthesized and characterized by IR spectroscopy, elemental analyses, room temperature magnetic susceptibility measurement and single-crystal X-ray diffraction technique. The structural analysis reveals a heterodinuclear association complex in which both the metal centers are found to be octahedrally coordinated. The complex cation, [Co(phen)₂(CN)₂]⁺, is bound to two cyanide ions in *cis* arrangement, while three cyanide groups are in a meridional position in the complex anion, [Fe(pzqc)(CN)₃]⁻.

Keywords : Cyanide-bound heterodinuclear FeCo complex, X-ray crystal structure, low-spin state of metal centers, IR spectroscopy.

Introduction

Since the discovery of a reversible thermally and photoinduced metal-to-metal electron transfer in the Prussian blue analogue K_{0.14}Co[Fe(CN)₆]_{0.71} \cdot 4 \cdot 93H₂O in 1996¹, an intense research activity has been directed to novel cyanide-based materials exhibiting tunable optical and magnetic properties as a function of external stimuli. This interest is driven in large part by the potential applications of such materials in energy efficient, switchable molecule-based information storage or electronic devices²⁻⁴. In fact, several attempts to design three dimensional (3-D) bimetallic cyanide-bridged networks have successfully led to switchable optical and magnetic molecule-based materials⁵⁻⁷. In these network assemblies, it is important to note that in most of the cases their high dimensionality makes a systematic study of magneto-structural relationships difficult, and their low solubility limits the shaping of these systems for technological applications.

In this research field, widespread research efforts have been devoted towards molecular fragments of Fe/Co Prussian blues with simple topology and improved solubility. Among these, [Fe₄Co₄], [Fe₂Co₂], [Fe₂Co₃], [Fe₄Co₂] and [Fe₂Co] core complexes have been extensively stu-

died⁸⁻¹⁴, and some of them exhibit both thermally- and photoinduced electron transfer, associated with the transformation of paramagnetic [Fe_{LS}^{III}-CN-Co_{HS}^{II}] pairs (LS = low-spin, HS = high-spin) into diamagnetic [Fe_{LS}^{II}-CN-Co_{LS}^{III}] pairs exactly like in the family of 3-D Fe/Co Prussian blue analogues.

We have recently reported a dinuclear cyano-bridged FeCo complex¹⁵ which was found to act as two different molecular switches depending on its physical state and external stimuli : spin crossover in solid-state induced by temperature, and intramolecular electron transfer in solution assisted by protonation¹⁵. Our continuing interest in the field of cyanide-based materials¹⁶⁻¹⁸, I report herein, synthesis and structural characterization of a heterodinuclear cyanide-bound FeCo association complex, [Co(phen)₂(CN)₂][Fe(pzqc)(CN)₃] \cdot 2 \cdot 5H₂O (**1**).

Experimental

Materials and physical measurements :

[(NBu₄)[Fe(pzqc)(CN)₃] \cdot 1 \cdot 5H₂O was synthesized according to the literature reported method¹⁸. All the analytical or reagent grade chemicals and solvents were purchased from commercial sources and used as received.

Microanalyses for C, H, and N were performed in a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. A FT-IR spectrum of the complex was recorded in the range of 400–4000 cm^{-1} on a Nicolet 750 Magna-IR spectrometer using KBr pellets. Conductivity measurements were made with a Systronics (model 304) direct reading conductivity meter. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature using an EG and G PAR-155 vibrating sample magnetometer, using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as reference material; diamagnetic correction was made by Pascal's constants for all the constituent atoms.

Synthesis of complex $[\text{Co}(\text{phen})_2(\text{CN})_2][\text{Fe}(\text{pzcq})(\text{CN})_3] \cdot 2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1) :

$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (29.2 mg, 0.10 mmol) and phenanthroline (phen) (39.6 mg, 0.20 mmol) were combined into a 20 ml of methanol, and the mixture was stirred for 20 min at room temperature. To the resulting solution a 20 ml methanolic solution of $[(\text{NBu}_4)[\text{Fe}(\text{pzcq})(\text{CN})_3] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (135 mg, 0.20 mmol) was added with stirring. The mixture was filtered and on standing at ambient temperature dark-red crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained from the solution after several days. Yield : 0.060 g, 64%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{30}\text{CoFeN}_{13}\text{O}_{3.50}$: C, 57.42; H, 3.36; N, 20.24. Found : C, 57.28; H, 3.22; N, 19.99%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3436 br (ν_{OH}), 1672 m ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$), 2114, 2129 m ($\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$); molar conductance : $86 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$; μ_{eff} 1.87 B.M.

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystal X-ray data of complex 1 were collected on a Bruker SMART APEX-II CCD diffractometer using graphite monochromated Mo $K\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Data collection, reduction, structure solution and refinement were performed using the Bruker Apex-II suite program. All available reflections to $2\theta_{\text{max}}$ were harvested and corrected for Lorentz and polarization factors with Bruker SAINT plus¹⁹. Empirical absorption correction, inter-frame scaling, and other systematic errors of the reflections were performed with SADABS¹⁹. The structure was solved by the direct methods and refined by means of full-matrix least-square technique based on F^2 with SHELX-97 software package²⁰. All the non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. Hydrogen atoms bound to carbon were placed in

calculated positions, while those attached to lattice water molecules were located in the difference Fourier map, and all of them were constrained to ride on their parent atoms. The crystal parameters and basic information relating to data collections and structure refinements for complex 1 are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement of complex 1

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{28}\text{CoFeN}_{13}\text{O}_{3.50}$
Formula weight	897.56
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Wavelength (\AA)	0.71073
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	$P\bar{1}$
a (\AA)	10.987(4)
b (\AA)	12.540(5)
c (\AA)	16.424(5)
α ($^\circ$)	67.542(2)
β ($^\circ$)	75.542(2)
γ ($^\circ$)	88.010(2)
Volume (\AA^3)	2020.4(13)
Z	2
D_{calc} (g cm^{-3})	1.475
Absorption coefficient (mm^{-1})	0.830
$F(000)$	916
θ Range for data collection ($^\circ$)	2.78–27.56
Limiting indices	$-14 = h = 14, -16 = k = 14,$ $-21 = l = 19$
Reflections collected/unique	15948
Independent reflection/ R_{int}	9211/0.0388
Observed reflections	6788
Parameters	548
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.056
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R1 = 0.0758,$ $wR2 = 0.1941$
R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.1040,$ $wR2 = 0.2155$

Results and discussion

Syntheses and general characterizations :

In my recent work, it has been observed that the reaction of $\text{Ph}_4\text{P}[\text{Fe}(\text{pzcq})(\text{CN})_3]$ with an aqueous-methanol solution of cobalt(II) nitrate exclusively yielded a heterobimetallic trinuclear Fe_2Co complex in which $[(\text{pzcq})\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_3]^-$ units act as a monodentate ligand through one of the three cyanides to the central cobalt(II) atom¹⁶.

In the present endeavor, treatment of $[(\text{NBu}_4)[\text{Fe}(\text{pzcq})(\text{CN})_3] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ with cobalt(II) nitrate in presence of a bidentate chelating ligand (phen) afforded a cyanide-bound heterodinuclear (FeCo) association complex **1** in high yield. Purity of the bulk sample was checked by elemental analyses. The molar conductivity measurement consistent with the crystal structure reveals that complex **1** is an 1 : 1 electrolyte type complex. The infrared spectra of **1** display two closely associated cyanide stretching absorptions ($2114, 2129 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) that are characteristic of those observed for related complexes^{26–28}. In addition to the cyanide stretching frequencies, a peak at 1672 cm^{-1} was observed which may be due the amide functionality present in pzcq ligand. A broad peak at 3436 cm^{-1} for OH stretching unambiguously suggests the involvement of extended hydrogen bonding of water molecules in crystal lattice.

Description of the crystal structures :

Complex **1** crystallizes in the triclinic $P\bar{1}$ space group, which consists of a complex cation $[\text{Co}(\text{phen})_2(\text{CN})_2]^+$, complex anion $[\text{Fe}(\text{pzcq})(\text{CN})_3]^-$ and some lattice water molecules. The perspective view of complex **1** along with a selected atom numbering scheme is depicted in Fig. 1, and important bond distances and bond angles are given in Table 2. Room temperature magnetic moment value of 1.87 BM clearly suggests that both of the metal ions are in low-spin state in complex **1**. This value is slightly higher than the spin-only value for a complex which contains isolated and isotropic $S = 1/2$ ion, suggesting that orbital contribution to the magnetic moment. The structure of

complex anion $[\text{Fe}(\text{pzcq})(\text{CN})_3]^-$ is pseudo-octahedron in which Fe atom is coordinated by three nitrogen atoms from pzcq ligand and three cyanide carbon atoms in meridional fashion. The Fe–C(cyano) [1.943(5)–1.952(5) Å] and Fe–N(pzcq) [1.885(4)–1.974(4) Å] bond lengths are in good agreement with those observed in other low-spin iron(III) complexes^{26–28}. The Fe–N(amide) distance (1.885 Å) is significantly shorter than the other two Fe–N lengths (1.961–1.974 Å) associated with pzcq ligand, which may be due to the presence of a strong δ -donor effect of the deprotonated amide nitrogen. The Fe–C \equiv N angles span in the very narrow range [177.9 (5)° to 179.0(4)°] and are close to linearity. Although terminal cyanides are linear enough, the significant structural distortion from the ideal octahedral geometry as reflected from the *transoid* angles around iron(III) center [165.68(17)–179.6(2)°] is mainly due to the shorter bite angles [82.74(17)–83.04(17)°] of coordinated pzcq ligand.

The structure of complex cation $[\text{Co}(\text{phen})_2(\text{CN})_2]^+$ is best described as a squashed octahedron, comprised of two phen ligands and two cyanide ions in *cis* dispositions. The Co–N(cyano) distances are in the range 1.878(5)–1.883(5) Å, which are comparable to those found in low-spin cobalt(III) complexes²⁹. The Co–N \equiv C bond angles [178.1(7)–178.9(5)°] are also very close to linearity, while bite angles of coordinated phen ligands [(83.7(2)–84.02(18)°] significantly deviate from ideal angle of 90°. This deviation has no impact on the overall geometry of the complex cation as *transoid* angles around cobalt(III)

Fig. 1. Crystal structure of **1** showing the selected atom numbering scheme. The hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity.

Fig. 2. A part of molecular packing showing hydrogen bonded supramolecular grid involving complex anion of **1** and lattice water molecules.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å), bond angles (°) and important hydrogen bonds (Å, °) for complex **1**

Bond lengths				
Co1–N8	1.966(4)	Fe1–N1	1.974(4)	
Co1–N9	1.930(4)	Fe1–N2	1.885(4)	
Co1–N10	1.974(4)	Fe1–N4	1.961(4)	
Co1–N11	1.943(5)	Fe1–C15	1.943(5)	
Co1–C42	1.878(5)	Fe1–C16	1.948(4)	
Co1–C43	1.883(5)	Fe1–C17	1.952(5)	
Bond angles				
N12–C42–Co1	178.1(7)	N5–C15–Fe1	178.2(4)	
N13–C43–Co1	178.9(5)	N6–C16–Fe1	177.9(5)	
N9–Co1–N11	174.9(2)	N7–C17–Fe1	179.0(4)	
C43–Co1–N8	177.6(2)	N2–Fe1–C16	179.6(2)	
N9–Co1–N8	84.02(18)	C15–Fe1–C17	170.7(2)	
C42–Co1–N10	177.6(3)	N2–Fe1–N4	82.74(17)	
N11–Co1–N10	83.7(2)	N2–Fe1–N1	83.04(17)	
		N4–Fe1–N1	65.68(17)	
Hydrogen bonds :				
D–H···A	D–H	H···A	D···A	<D–H···A
O2–H2B···N7	0.85	1.97(1)	2.808(7)	169.0
O3–H3A···N6	0.89	2.00(3)	2.787(11)	152.0
O3–H3B···N6a	0.90	2.10(3)	2.863(10)	143.0
O2–H2A···N5b	0.85	2.00(5)	2.842(7)	170.0
Symmetry code : a = 1+x, y, z; b = -x, -y, 1-z				

are close enough to the ideal angles of 180°. Careful inspection of crystal structure shows that the molecular packing is stabilized by the strong hydrogen bonding interaction involving cyanide nitrogen, amide oxygen of pzcq ligand and lattice water molecules (Table 2). Interestingly, lattice water molecules and cyanide nitrogen atoms from complex anion **1** form supramolecular aggregates through hydrogen bonded square-like grid as shown in Fig. 2. Moreover, moderately strong several π - π stacking interactions are observed between the aromatic rings of adjacent molecules.

Conclusion

A new cyanide-bound heterodinuclear FeCo association complex is reported. X-Ray crystal structure reveals that the compound is constructed by a complex cation $[\text{Co}(\text{phen})_2(\text{CN})_2]^+$, and a complex anion $[\text{Fe}(\text{pzcq})(\text{CN})_3]^-$, in which each of the metal center is hexa-coordinated. Two cyanide ions are *cis* coordinated in the complex cation, while they are in meridionally disposed in the complex anion. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility data suggest that both the metal centers are in low-spin state.

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Supplementary data

CCDC 939170 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for **1**, respectively. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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